

Viscosity and Apparent Molal Volume of Solutions of Strontium Chloride in Dioxane-Water Mixtures at 35°.

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The viscosity and the apparent molal volume of strontium chloride in dioxane-water mixtures at 10, 20 and 30% by weight of dioxane have been studied at 35°. The viscosity data fit well with the modified form of the Jones-Dole equation and the constant 'B' has been found to be dependent on the solvent composition. The apparent molal volume data is satisfactorily represented by the Masson's equation and the apparent molal volume (Φ_v) at zero concentration has been found to be dependent on the solvent composition.

In extension of our previous investigations^{1,2}, the viscosity and apparent molal volume of Strontium chloride in 10, 20 and 30% dioxane-water mixtures by weight have been determined at 35°.

EXPERIMENTAL

SrCl₂ used was of E. P. E. Merck variety. The Cl⁻ content was estimated by standard methods³. The preparation of the solvents, solutions, and measurements of the viscosity and density were the same as reported earlier⁴. The viscometer and the pycnometer used were of the type used by Chakravarty and Prasad.⁵ In both the cases precautions were taken to prevent the evaporation of the solvent.

TABLE I

Concentration in moles/litre.	10% Dioxane		20% Dioxane.		30% Dioxane	
	η/η_0 abs.	η/η_0 cal.	η/η_0 abs.	η/η_0 cal.	η/η_0 abs.	η/η_0 cal.
0.1	1.0391	1.0396	1.0524	1.0518	1.0538	1.0595
0.075	1.0204	1.0302	1.0327	1.0390	1.0354	1.0434
0.05	1.0165	1.0207	1.0256	1.0264	1.0290	1.0306
0.025	1.0114	1.0110	1.0154	1.0135	1.0155	1.0153
0.01	1.0089	1.0047	1.0096	1.0059	1.0097	1.0064
0.0075	1.0078	1.0038	1.0085	1.0045	1.0084	1.0049
0.005	1.0052	1.0028	1.0052	1.0032	1.0055	1.0033
0.0025	1.0040	1.0015	1.0038	1.0019	1.0040	1.0019
0.001	1.0026	1.0008	—	—	1.0026	1.0010

1. Das *et al.*, *This Journal.*, 1965, 42, 166.

2. Das *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1966, 43, 58.

3. Vogel, "Text book of Quantitative Analysis."

4. Acharya *et al.*, *This Journal.*, 1957, 34, 56.

5. Prasad *et al.*, *Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1938, 34, 1934.

TABLE II

Solvent compn.	$A \times 10^6$	X	B	Φ_0	'a'
10	1.200	0.99	0.35	19.50	0.916
20	1.265	1.02	0.50	15.00	1.250
30	1.328	1.04	0.62	12.50	5.000

DISCUSSION

The relative viscosity of SrCl_2 in 10, 20 and 30% solvent composition (weight % of dioxane) were directly determined. The procedure for testing the Jones Dole equation by plotting $\eta/\eta_0 - 1/\sqrt{C}$ against $\sqrt{C}$ has been applied and the equation does not hold good, for the data. However, these data are satisfactorily represented by the modified form¹.

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC'$$

The constant 'A', associated with the electrostatic properties of the ions in solutions, were calculated from Falkenhagen and Vernon¹ expression. The values of 'B' and 'X' were determined from the intercept and slope respectively of the line obtained by plotting $\log \{\eta/\eta_0 - (1 + A\sqrt{C})\}$ against $\log c$. The relative viscosities were calculated, using these determined values of 'B' & 'X'. The calculated and the observed values are in fair agreement and are tabulated in table I. In table II, the values of 'A', 'B' and 'X' are recorded.

From the large number of experimental data collected from the measurements made with aqueous solutions of various electrolytes, the nature of 'B' has given rise to a number of speculations, namely additive character of 'B' by Cox and Wolfenden⁶ and Kaminsky⁷ and lyotropic number by Aasmus⁸ and the ion dipole interaction between the ions and the solvent by Nightingale⁹. In taking into account the behaviour of electrolytes in the mixed solvents, containing large proportions of water, not only the behaviour of ions in aqueous solution has to be kept in picture, but also the influence of the third kind of molecules present as the solvent and this extent of modifying the properties of ion solvent interaction on the charge, size and extent of hydration has got to be taken care of. It has been suggested that the occurrence of the 'B' term in the Jones-Dole equation is largely associated with the solvation of the ions. When a mixture of dioxane-water is employed as solvent, it is but natural to expect the solvation sphere to be composed of both the kind of molecules i.e., dioxane and water. The change in viscosity and naturally the 'B' value will change depending to the extent to which the dioxane molecule influence the ions by their presence in the solvation sphere. This may arise by promoting disorder of the structure of water in the solvation sphere and thereby increasing the size of the ion or by combined effect of both. Earlier studies¹ in case of monovalent salts in dioxane-water mixture clearly indicate that the viscosity of the solution increases due to the presence of dioxane

6. Cox *et al.*, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1934, 145A, 425.

7. Kaminsky, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1957, 12a, 424.

8. Aasmus, *ibid.*, 1949, 4a, 589.

9. Nightingale, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 1381.

in the medium and thus an increase in 'B' value is noticed and this 'B' value progressively increases as the dioxane content in the medium increases. It can be seen from the table II, that the values of 'B' progressively increases with the increase in dioxane content. This suggests that the presence of dioxane in the solvation sphere promotes the ordering of the water structure round an ion, in solvents of low dioxane content (10% of dioxane) but with higher amount of dioxane say 20% and 30% an orientation of the dioxane with respect to the ions takes place, which also exhibits a large increase in viscosity (table I).

The apparent molal volume (Φ) is most conveniently calculated from the density of the solution and solvent by means of the equation:
$$\Phi = \frac{M}{\rho_0} - \left(\frac{\rho - \rho_0}{\rho_0}\right) \frac{10^3}{C}$$
 where M is the molecular weight of the solute, C is the concentration in moles per litre and ρ and ρ_0 are the densities of the solutions and solvents respectively. The data obtained have been found to agree with Masson's⁸ equation as the plot of Φ against $\sqrt{C}$ is linear. The values of Φ_0 , the apparent molal volume at zero concentration and the constant 'a' could be calculated from the intercept and the slope respectively. These values are recorded in table II.

From table II (column V and VI), it is seen that the value of Φ_0 decreases with the increase in dioxane content. This change in the value of Φ_0 , can probably be due to the change in the orientation of the dioxane with respect to the ions. With respect to the dependence of Φ_0 on the composition of the solvent i.e. dioxane and water, further investigations are in progress.

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